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Effective Customer Service as A Key Driver of Business Success in the Contemporary and Competitive Market

Amos Ojo Adedeji, PhD

Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract: In recent years, marketing has become the bedrock of business; equally customer satisfaction has grown in importance in all commercial organisations. The study interrogated the effectiveness of good customer service in the modern day and competitive business dealings. The study is descriptive in nature relying mainly on secondary source of data collection and analysis. The work found customer loyalty, positive relationship with increased profit, higher inventory turnover of the organisation, personal satisfaction and fulfillment of customers, and higher morale of employee as the effect of good customer service. However, effectiveness of customer service is been defied by a number of barriers, namely negative first impression, dichotomy, superior-subordinate relationships, non-caring culture and lack of adequate training among others. The work concluded that customer satisfaction has become a crucial factor in determining the accomplishment of a business organisation in the contemporary and competitive corporate world. The study recommended good first impression, team work, cordial relationship between senior and junior staff, staff motivation, and prioritise train and retrain of staff.

Keywords: *Business, Customer, Customer Service Representative, Organisation, Satisfaction*

1. Introduction

Today's highly competitive corporate environment has made customer satisfaction more than just a catchphrase. It has grown to be an important determinant of an organization's long-term survival and success (Praveen and Thippeswamy, 2023). A defined mission is the foundation for an organisation's understanding of its competitive advantages and market position.

Customer is a boss, regardless of whether his work is a menial job or he is in charge of the largest company in the world. Customer determines whether a business will prosper. According to Bellou (2007), customer has the ability to determine which business will endure and which will eventually go into liquidation. It implies that every action taken,

every idea considered, and every piece of technology created and used is focused on making the customer satisfied.

Businesses constantly look for fresh and creative approaches to provide high-quality customer service as a competitive edge to draw in new clients, keep existing ones, and turn a profit (Khan and Fasih, 2014). The current competitive market environment has forced service organisations to look for fresh and creative approaches to preserve organisational effectiveness while also satisfying customers.

It is often accepted that one of the key elements affecting customer happiness is providing exceptional customer service. The customer service role has become more crucial to the success of many organizations

as the modern service society has grown (Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler, 2006). Customer Service Representatives (CSR) have a big influence on how customers feel about the company and how they perceive it overall. The primary objective of the study was to interrogate the effectiveness of good customer service in the 21st century competitive business relations.

1b. Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to cross-examine the effectiveness of good customer service in the modern day and competitive business environment.

2. Literature Review

Customer service is serving clients prior to, during, and following a purchase. Additionally, it entails providing services and all interactions for the customer. Customer service is a collection of activities meant to increase the level of customer satisfaction, or the conviction that a product or a service has met the client's requirements and expectations (Jamier, 2002). Agreeing with Lovelock, Patterson, and Walker (2007), customer service is a task-oriented activity that entails face-to-face, telephone, or email with customers in person for service delivery.

Further, customer service is a high-quality product or service that meets a customer's needs and desires and encourages continued business. Additional benefits of providing excellent customer service include increased revenues, job satisfaction, teamwork, company morale, market development of services and goods, and continuous success. Good fundamental customer services are defined as those that are timely, effective, helpful, and pleasant. Gaining customer trust and loyalty, which is the foundation of client retaining, is the goal of providing exceptional customer service (Kotler, 2002).

Personal and interpersonal skills including language, posture, gestures, listening comprehension, and telephone tactics can all be used to demonstrate customer service

effectively. It is a series of steps used to increase the level of client satisfaction, or the belief that a product or service has fulfilled expectations. Customer service can be delivered automatically through self-service or by a human (such as a sales and service agent). Customer satisfaction and operational efficiency are two goals that should guide the design, execution, and communication of customer service.

Perception of service by the customers' perceptions of quality of service is influenced by a variety of aspects, ranging from the process to the end result. Grönroos (2001) asserts that "quality is what customers perceive". When evaluating the service, consumers take into account all factors that affect the procedure and the end result. However, as Zeithaml et al. (2006) noted, the customer's subjective evaluation of the actual service experiences is the customer's perceived service quality.

The aspect of human interaction in service delivery that consists of human behaviour and attitudes is a primary focus of a thorough examination of the quality aspects. The majority of researchers agreed on these aspects of service quality as a measure of service quality. Looy et al. (2003) shared a view that customers are not one dimensional in their judgment because many other factors influence service quality.

Numerous service management studies have demonstrated that a customer's assessment of the quality of services is shaped by their evaluation of numerous interactions with a company. According to Zeithaml et al (2006), "customers perceive services in terms of quality of the service and how satisfied they are overall with their experiences". Nonetheless, these interactions are primarily the result of collaboration between the staff members who interact with the customer and the clients themselves, who may be better able to comprehend them and address any issues pertaining to the services.

3. Methodology

The study interrogated the relationship between good customer service and customer satisfaction in the 21st century competitive business relations. The work employed the use of descriptive method of research which is historical in nature. Thus, data collection was mainly restricted to secondary source, which includes but not limited to textbooks, journals, magazines, conference papers, and other related publications of eminent academics on the theme of marketing and customer relations.

The study utilised content analysis to analyse the collated data in line with its historical method. The validity of the topic of the study affects current competitive approach of business across the globe, and this has been painstakingly examined. This study therefore drew insights from various marketing approaches.

4. Result and Discussion

Customer Service Satisfaction

The quality of the service provided determines the level of customer satisfaction, even though what one customer views as exceptional may not be the same for another. Customer satisfaction is measured by how well company's products and services meet or surpass the expectations of its customers. In a market where companies compete for customers, customer satisfaction is seen as a critical differentiator and has become increasingly significant as a corporate strategic element.

Customer satisfaction is an asset that must be monitored and managed, just like any other tangible asset. Understanding customer demands has become essential in today's market, thus businesses in this sector have shifted from product-centric to customer-centric roles. The kind of service offered affects customer satisfaction. The most significant factor influencing an organization's ability to survive is customer satisfaction.

Focusing on customer service quality as one of the customer satisfaction elements has the

most significant impact on customer retention. Proactively measuring client impressions and taking swift action on the results are essential for gaining a competitive edge. Customer satisfaction is related to both products and services and can be felt in a number of contexts.

Customer expectations have a big impact on this very subjective evaluation. Additionally, customer satisfaction is determined by client results as well as their interaction with the company which is referred to in business literature as the "moment of truth". According to some scholars, a satisfied client in the private sector is "one who receives significant added value" to his or her bottom line; this definition might as well be applicable to public services.

The situation and the product or service have an impact on customer satisfaction. A consumer may be pleased with a service or product, an experience, a choice to buy, a salesman, a retailer, a service provider, an attribute, or a mix of these. Since "satisfaction" is "too fuzzy an idea to serve as a meaningful benchmark," some academics steer clear of it entirely as a quantitative aim. Rather, they concentrate on the customer's complete interaction with a company or service provider and the thorough evaluation of that interaction.

Individual expectations have a significant impact on customer satisfaction, which is a very subjective evaluation. Some definitions are predicated on the finding that individual expectations about a service or product are either confirmed or not, which leads to consumer satisfaction or discontent. According to some experts, businesses should "concentrate on a goal that's more closely linked to customer equity" in order to prevent issues arising from the vast array of customer expectations and disparities.

Companies should be encouraged to find out how customers hold them accountable rather than focusing on whether they are satisfied. Customers evaluate the quality of the service,

but their level of satisfaction with the entire experience determines how satisfied they are. The performance of the customer service representative in comparison to the customer's expectations determines whether the consumer is happy after making a purchase.

There is a difference between customer happiness and service quality despite their frequent interchangeability (Zeithaml et al, 2006). When the results of the service meet the expectations of the client, the customer is satisfied. According to Zeithaml et al. (2006), it is the customer's assessment of a product or service based on whether or not it has fulfilled his needs or expectations that matter.

Depending on the demands the client had prior to the service, satisfaction can be expressed in a variety of ways, which include feelings of relief, ambivalence, pleasure, delight, fulfillment, and contentment. It is dynamic and changes over time under the effect of numerous causes, despite the fact that it is often assessed as a static metric. One of the elements that affects customer happiness is service quality; in other words, it is a component of the customer satisfaction metric.

A customer's level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction is determined by how well a product or service meets their needs or expectations (Zeithaml et al, 2006). If a company's consumers are happy with the services they receive, they will remain loyal to the company and will be retained, which is good for the company because it may also result in increased revenue, a larger market share, and a larger customer base.

Customer dissatisfaction does not equate to customer satisfaction because customers value quality and satisfaction in a variety of ways (Kondo, 2001). Changes in satisfaction are a result of previous choices because consumers evaluate quality, and the most significant way to measure quality is by how it impacts customer satisfaction.

Similarly, Herrmann, Huber, and Braunstein (2000) contended that a customer's perception

of the quality of their product determines whether or not they believe it meets their expectations, or whether they are satisfied. Customer satisfaction and the company's financial success are positively correlated. Customer satisfaction is perhaps a key factor in determining a business's profitability.

More businesses are beginning to understand how crucial customer satisfaction is to their future success (Johnson and Fornell, 1991). Understanding what customers want is essential when trying to improve customer satisfaction. Berry et al. (1985) identified ten dimensions of customer satisfaction, which are listed below:

- (1) **Access:** Access is described as the ease with which a service can be obtained, which includes waiting times, contact methods, and the service provider's flexible working hours.
- (2) **Communication:** This is how information is shared by the service delivery and absorbed by clients. It includes sympathetic listening, the use of everyday language, and an explanation of the service's benefits and drawbacks.
- (3) **Competence:** It refers to the degree of expertise and understanding possessed by the customer service providers displayed to the clients.
- (4) **Courtesy:** This is the kindness and civility demonstrated by the service providers to the customer mostly during challenging time.
- (5) **Credibility:** It is the faith that clients have in the company and the employees who deliver the service.
- (6) **Reliability:** This refers to the ability to consistently provide appropriate service at the right time, correctly done the first time devoid of letting down the customer.
- (7) **Responsiveness:** It is the readiness and desire of staff to offer prompt assistance as at when due to the customer.

- (8) **Security:** This is the protection against risk, uncertainty, and danger. It suggests privacy and physical security.
- (9) **Tangible:** This is the proof that the organization and its services are reliable and trustworthy as evaluated by client.
- (10) **Understanding:** It is the degree to which the company is aware of what its clients anticipate from the services it offers and deliver accordingly.

It should be noted that higher percentage of the aforementioned elements are required to accomplish the stated goal rather than all of them being present for a client to be satisfied. Customer satisfaction is a model that talks about the features of product and service, and how they affect customer satisfaction. The traits are divided into three categories of delighters, satisfiers, and dissatisfies.

Dissatisfies are qualities that consumers anticipate from a product or service. Customers may not be able to identify qualities needed in a product or service; nevertheless, they still assume or expect them to be present. Satisfiers are qualities that consumers desire in a good or service that makes them satisfy, while delighters are novel and inventive features of goods or services that the consumer does not anticipate. However, their presence is a tactic to draw in new customers.

Positive and Negative Aspects of Customer Satisfaction

In line with literature of customer service, there are identified positive and negative aspects of customer satisfaction.

Positive Aspects

Higher economic returns are more likely to be obtained by businesses that aim for greater customer satisfaction. They also understand that financial gains take time to materialise. Business prospects can be predicted by customer satisfaction since satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal to the company, which suggests steady cash flow in the future. Anderson et al. (1994)

support this by recognising the positive correlation.

High customer satisfaction has several advantages for a firm, and there is a belief that there is a positive correlation between economic success and customer satisfaction (Anderson et al, 1994). Additionally, it will help to build a loyal customer base and reduce price sensitivity in customers, all of which point to steady future cash flow.

Any business with satisfied customers will inevitably grow its clientele and, consequently its profitability. Either intentionally or inadvertently, satisfied customers may promote the company to the outside world. Therefore, it is crucial for service sectors to offer clients high-quality service in order to ultimately satisfy, win their loyalty, and keep them as clients.

Negative Aspects

Customers who are satisfied with a product or service are more likely to make constant purchases and have higher expectations for the future (Rust and Oliver, 2000). However, the company will have a harder time satisfying customers in the upcoming purchase cycle and maintaining the same level of customer satisfaction in the future because of their heightened expectations. In the long term, this could hurt the business.

Additionally, Rust and Oliver (2000) questioned the worthy goal of achieving high customer satisfaction, and contend that businesses do not benefit from such because it only creates difficult-to-achieve expectations and raises the costs associated with higher expectations. Also, Anderson et al. (1997) contended that the expense and pursuit of customer satisfaction will impair the company's production. To maintain the required degree of satisfaction, the company must work harder to improve the product's features or general design in addition to raising prices.

Principle of Good Customer Service

Principle is defined as a set of rules or policy that guides the operation of a person, group of people or an organisation in the day-to-day activities. It dictates the dos and don'ts of the organisation. Hunninghake and York (2012) highlighted ten (10) golden rules of good customer service namely:

- 1) **A Customer In Need Is A Customer Indeed:** It is assuming there is a problem when the differences between your product and that of your competitor are minimal. The quality of service you provide to customers must differ significantly from that of your competitors. Organisation customer service department need to render quality and sustained service to their customer
- 2) **Hire People with Good Customer Skills:** Search out for the great employees most especially those who have already worked with high humanitarian motives, and those you have accessed and sure they can deliver. Find out the qualities the employees have in common from their boss. Employees with team work aspiration should be considered instead of employees with individualistic ambition.
- 3) **Train Employees On Company Policies:** Let the policies of the organisation be a watchword to your employees. Be a man or woman of objectivity, be the example for your employees to emulate. Don't ask your employees to do something you wouldn't do. Demonstrate high quality and efficiency as part of your service to the organisation.
- 4) **Cross Train Your Employees:** Provide opportunities for staff members to learn. Competent workers enhance their abilities in a variety of professional and personal domains. They have the option of doing it alone or choosing to go somewhere else for extra learning and challenge. They can also study under your guidance and form strong bonds with your company in the process. This is by given detailed description of the task expected to be done, and the expected outcomes.
- 5) **Teach Your Staff How to Develop Rapport:** Show your staff how to use human interaction to provide exceptional customer service. Friendliness should be the motive of customer service as first impression last longer. Customers are ever ready to share their experience with representative who is friendly, humble as well as active.
- 6) **Know Your Customers Names:** Customer Service Representatives should be assertive, brilliant as well as humorous, and avoid discussing sensitive personal topics. Remember this when working with people that everyone has an invisible sign that reads, "make me feel important," hanging from their neck.
- 7) **Teach Your Staff to Pose Open-Ended Questions:** People are encouraged to discuss anything that is significant to them when they are asked open-ended questions. It facilitates communication, information gathering, and comprehension. Open ended questions will allow customers to pour out their heart to the representative, show a sign of seriousness when listening to them. Paraphrase the question for clarity purposes.
- 8) **Instill A Sense Of Urgency In Helping Customers:** Don't be delayed in asserting yes to customer, delay may be dangerous. Be affirmative always while dealing with customers. Affirmations are declarations that highlight a client's talents and behaviours no matter how minor that move them closer to positive change. It increases self-confidence in one's capacity for transformation. Affirmations need to be sincere and consistent in order to be successful. Sincerity and integrity are essential components of genuine service that cannot be purchased or quantified in monetary terms.
- 9) **Handle Distressed Customers With Care:** Handling annoyed or unhappy

individuals requires a unique set of abilities and tolerance. Regardless of the customer's behaviour, make an effort to react professionally and cheerfully while maintaining composure and focus. Keeping focused on the problem, rather the emotions will aid identification of the source of the customer's dissatisfaction. Customer support agent should carefully identify a disgruntled consumer, acknowledge their own emotions, get clarity, and address the matter. This is a fantastic method to assist clients in making positive life decisions.

- 10) **Don't Let An Unhappy Customer Leave Your Office:** Try all means available to you to make sure no customer leave you unhappy. Focus on listening to the customer's point of view on the issue and speak in a serious yet upbeat and supportive manner. Through successful communication, be empathised by showing the customer that you understand their displeasure or disappointment.

Customer Service Skills and Competencies

The definition and features of the notion used to characterise the skills necessary to provide customer service has recently become subject of debate (Adedeji, 2022). Several terms are frequently used interchangeably by various authors to describe a person's disposition, interpersonal, communication, and teamwork skills. Bolton (2004) acknowledged that many facets of customer service job that may not be acknowledged as skilled and makes reference to emotional work.

Skills and knowledge are seen as superficial traits that are easier to acquire through training and are more readily apparent to others. A person's self-concept, attributes, and motivations are more essential to their personality than their less obvious or concealed traits, making them more challenging to develop (Cran, 1994). CSR need a variety of competencies and skills to succeed. The most practical customer service skills include, but are not limited to:

- (1) **Honesty and Integrity:** Clients want to believe they can rely on service provider for the quality of the goods and services provided.
- (2) **Recovering from Mistakes:** How service provider handles mistakes and the remedies he/she provides are frequently used by customers to assess the quality of company service. If the issue is eventually resolved to the satisfaction of the customer, they are typically quite forgiving of errors.
- (3) **Enthusiasm:** Customer service employees must show their clients that the work they do for them is significant and valuable.
- (4) **Customer Service Representative Word:** CSR need to avoid making commitments or promises that they can't fulfill in their role. However, service provider should establish realistic and effective expectations.
- (5) **Eye Contact:** CSR should gaze directly into the clients' eyes, and speak to customers directly.
- (6) **Shaking Hands:** A solid and business-like handshake is anticipated when CSR shake hands with customers.
- (7) **Kind Tone:** Always project warmth and friendliness. No matter how challenging or exhausting CSR are, they need to avoid raising their voice in unwarranted annoyance or rage. There should be enough space between CSR and consumer when uneasy. For customers to feel safe and unthreatened there must be enough space.
- (8) **Observation:** CSR must pay attention to how the client acts and what they respond favorably to when are serving them.
- (9) **Posture:** CSR should project openness, warmth, and attention with their posture. To show the customer that you are interested, lean forward, face them, and nod.

Bernthal and Davis (1998) also highlight the following as part of the customer service skills to be excellent in their service:

- 01) **Customer Sensitivity:** Exhibits consideration for the opinions and sentiments of customers.
- 02) **Decisiveness:** Chooses actions to fulfill the needs of customers.
- 03) **Flexibility:** Adapts style to the demands and preferences of customers.
- 04) **Impact:** Maintains neat appearance and positive impression.
- 05) **Job Knowledge:** Comprehends the policies and processes of the organization and its clients.
- 06) **Motivation to Serve Customers:** Finds joy and contentment in interacting with clients.
- 07) **Planning:** Arranges tasks and gets ready for meetings with clients.
- 08) **Situation Analysis:** Compiles and examines data regarding the circumstances of clients.

Effect of Good Customer Service on Client Satisfaction

According to Bowen and Chen (2001), a merely pleased customer is insufficient; there must be exceptionally satisfied customers. The rationale is that client loyalty must follow from customer satisfaction. Building customer loyalty is now the only option for organizations to create a sustained competitive advantage, according to Bansal and Gupta (2001). While satisfaction is a prerequisite for loyalty, it is not a sufficient one. To put it another way, we can be satisfied without being loyal, but it is difficult to be loyal without being satisfied.

It is well recognized that profitability and customer loyalty are positively correlated (Bowen and Chen, 2001). Marketers are looking for advice on how to increase client loyalty these days. Reduced marketing expenses, higher sales, and lower operating expenses all contribute to the higher profit. Loyal consumers are less expensive to serve

because they are familiar with the product and need less information. They also serve as a source of information for other customers.

Organizations must be able to predict the needs of their customers in order to guarantee customer loyalty. Kandampully and Duffy (1999) assert that a company's capacity to predict a customer's future wants and provide them before anyone else does, will determine the customer's desire in preserving a loyal connection.

Comprehensively, good customer service will make the organisation to grow while both the service provider and customer will benefit immensely from the service. The benefit of good customer service is breakdown into three, namely the beneficiaries, the provider and the organisation. Higher income, recognition, personal satisfaction and fulfillment, and less stress are positive effects accrued to the customers which stand as beneficiaries.

The provider of the service is responsible for the task of attending to customer. They are attached with high self-awareness and self-control, greater authenticity, more repeat business, constant referred business, fewer returns, better reputation, higher morale, and happier employee. The organisation is also referred to as the company. Higher staff turnover, less complaints, increased productivity, a better workplace, increased inventory turnover, and increased revenues are all advantages for the company.

Challenges of Customer Service Satisfaction

Life endeavor is mostly not problem-free as there are hindrances envisage or not envisage that come on the way of human being. Customer Service is not an exception as it has its own hitches. Some of the barriers to effective customer service include but not limited to:

- 1) **Negative First Impression:** First impression lasts longer, and has the ability to set the tone for all future transactions.

Failure of customer service representative to make good or positive first impression to a customer can cause the organisation a lot of exploit. Showing unimpressive attitude to a first timer is disadvantageous to both the company and the officer. The veracity is that people prefer doing business with those who treat them warmly at their first encounter.

- 2) **Overworked Staff:** Understaffing, layoffs, quick growth, or giving too many tasks to too few people can all contribute to overwork. As a result of this, staff will quickly lose their energy which will make service representative to be sluggish in responding or not able to respond to the need of customer. As a result, clients will become enraged as their problems are not receiving adequate attention.
- 3) **Dichotomy:** Dichotomy among the Customer Service Representative and other units will give birth to factions, differences of opinion, conflict of interests, suspicion among and between various units that constitute the organisation. It will hinder the efforts of service units and produce negative result. The goal becomes individual survival instead of team success. Hence achieving company's goals become a difficult task.
- 4) **Superior-Subordinate Relationships:** The result of an organisation where junior is treated as a mere slave or not part of the organisation is deficiency and this will naturally affect customer service unit. In such a situation, inferiority complex sets in, the subordinate staff will have to depend on the superior officer before taken decision even in an emergency case.
- 5) **Non-Caring Culture:** The culture of the workplace can be significantly impacted by how customer service situations are handled. A company where staff is not empowering in return for their work, it is likely the CSR will not show customers enough concern to make them satisfied.
- 6) **Lack of Adequate Training:** Many companies found it difficult to specifically train their staff in act of modern customer service strategy. Also, many establishments lack the attitude of prioritising training as a necessity and where it is prioritised, it is not been implemented to the letter, and hence affects the effectiveness and efficiency of the company (Adedeji, 2021). Further, the staff did not always value it and thereby take it with levity or absent from said training. Lack of effective training policies and poor top management support is also a deficient
- 7) **Poor Communication Value:** Everyone in the company, from the manager to the cleaner, is accountable for ensuring that customers are satisfied. The importance of customers must always be emphasised to all employees. Customer satisfaction has been threatened by employees' incapacity to treat customers with respect and decency.

5. Conclusion

The quality of service rendered by customer service representatives determines the customer satisfaction and hence the success of the company. The study interrogated the effectiveness of customer service on the company. The work established that customer satisfaction has become an essential element in determining the success and long-term viability of a business organisation in the contemporary and competitive corporate world. Hence, companies have unremittingly sought for innovative means of offering quality service for customer satisfaction.

The paper has held that the trios of business organisation, customer service representatives and customers will benefit immensely from effective customer service. The study highlighted a number of factors that serve as stumbling block to the effective customer service. To address the identified challenges, business organisation in collaboration with CSR coupled with entire employees must implement the recommendations of the paper to the letter.

Recommendations

Industries must comprehend and take into account the identified obstacles to providing excellent customer service. Through the identification of barriers, the following recommendations are provided for effective customer service:

- (1) All entrepreneurs understand the significance of creating a favourable first impression. A competent customer service representative establishes a rapport with potential clients almost immediately. Making a good impression on the customer is essential to earning their confidence and trust. Making a good first impression is crucial since it can influence all subsequent interactions.
- (2) Customer Service Representatives need to be genuinely responsive to customers' needs. The few minutes it takes to respond promptly can save countless hours later while attempting to keep a failing placement intact. Resolving a customer's issue effectively can turn their displeasure into satisfaction and retain them as customers. According to research, a genuine, considerate, and astute reaction to an issue can help businesses keep ninety-five percent of their unsatisfied clients.
- (3) Team work among the customer service representatives and other units is recommended. This will boost their efforts to achieve more than individual dichotomy. Team spirit is an essential strategy in achieving company's goals.
- (4) Company should make it as point of concern to encourage cordial relationship between the senior and the junior staff. The relationships should not be a master/servant, but a parent/children affair.
- (5) Staff in charge of customers' needs should always be motivated by the company. This will surely increase the staff ability to discharge their duty well and add extra strength to achieve company's goal.
- (6) Company should enhance the experience of customers by contributing to their efforts to ensure that all customer service representatives are developed for efficient and effective delivery. The organisation should make it as a matter of priority to always train and retrain the CSR. The training should involve both technical and interactive quality.
- (7) Good communication value is highly recommended. Customer Service Representative must learn the act courtesy, and endeavour to satisfy customers. Ability to treat customers with respect and decency is fundamental.

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